

TO COMPARE EVALUATION PARAMETERS OF BRANDED AND GENERIC PREPARATION OF METRONIDAZOLE TABLET

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ABSTRACT

The present study was undertaken to compare the pharmaceutical quality control parameters of branded and generic preparations of Metronidazole 400 mg tablets. Both formulations were evaluated for general appearance, solubility, melting point, UV-Visible spectroscopic analysis (calibration curve, λ_{max} , drug content), weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration, moisture content, and dissolution profile. The λ_{max} of Metronidazole was found to be 319.7 nm with $R^2 = 0.9805$ confirming linearity (Beer–Lambert's law). Drug content for branded tablets ranged from 97.94% to 99.05% and for generic tablets from 98.97% to 99.72%, both within acceptable IP limits. Weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration, and moisture content results were within pharmacopeial limits for both formulations. Dissolution studies revealed that branded tablets achieved approximately

96–99% drug release at 60 minutes, while generic tablets showed 95–99% drug release at the same time point. The results indicate that both branded and generic Metronidazole tablet formulations comply with official pharmacopeial standards and are pharmaceutically equivalent, suggesting that the generic preparation can serve as a cost-effective alternative to the branded product.

KEYWORDS: Metronidazole, Generic medicine, Branded medicine, Tablet evaluation, Dissolution study, Pharmaceutical equivalence.

INTRODUCTION

Medicines play an essential role in the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of diseases. Pharmaceutical products are mainly categorized into branded medicines and generic medicines, both containing the same Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) but differing in brand name, price, and marketing strategies.^[1]

Branded medicines are originally developed by pharmaceutical companies after extensive research, clinical trials, and regulatory approval. These medicines are marketed under a specific brand name and are usually protected by patents for a certain period. Due to research and promotional costs, branded medicines are often more expensive.

Generic medicines are produced after the expiry of the patent of the innovator drug. Generic drugs contain the same API, strength, dosage form, route of administration, quality, safety, and therapeutic efficacy as their branded counterparts. They are generally more affordable because manufacturers do not bear the initial research and development expenses.

According to regulatory authorities such as the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) and guidelines of the Indian Pharmacopoeia, generic medicines must demonstrate pharmaceutical equivalence and bioequivalence with branded medicines. Various quality control parameters such as weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration time, and dissolution studies are performed to ensure their quality and performance.^[2]

The increasing healthcare cost has emphasized the importance of generic medicines in improving patient accessibility and reducing economic burden. However, misconceptions regarding the quality and effectiveness of generic drugs still exist among patients and healthcare professionals. Therefore, the present study aims to compare generic and branded Metronidazole 400 mg tablets based on pharmaceutical quality control tests to evaluate whether generic medicines provide comparable performance to branded formulations.^[3]

Metronidazole

Metronidazole (MNZ) is an antiprotozoal and antibacterial drug belonging to the nitroimidazole class of antimicrobial agents. It is effective against anaerobic bacteria and certain protozoal infections and is widely used in the treatment of amebiasis, trichomoniasis, giardiasis, bacterial vaginosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, anaerobic bacterial infections, and *Clostridium difficile* infections.^[15,16] The drug exhibits rapid, concentration-dependent

bactericidal activity. Its mechanism of action involves passive diffusion into the organism, reductive activation, interaction with host cell DNA causing strand breakage and helix destabilization, and breakdown of cytotoxic products, ultimately causing cell death in susceptible anaerobic organisms.^[15,16]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Metronidazole drug (reference standard), branded Metronidazole 400 mg tablets, generic Metronidazole 400 mg tablets, distilled water, alcohol, chloroform, and dimethylformamide (DMF) were used in the study.

2.2 Equipment

Weighing balance, UV–Visible Spectrophotometer, pH meter, Monsanto Hardness Tester, Digital Moisture Analyzer, Friability Tester (Roche Friabilator), Disintegration Test Apparatus, and Dissolution Test Apparatus were used.

2.3 General Appearance

Twenty tablets of each formulation (branded and generic) were visually inspected under uniform lighting for color, shape, odor, surface defects (chips, cracks), coating uniformity, and any markings.^[18]

2.4 Solubility

Solubility of Metronidazole was determined by taking approximately 1–2 mg of drug in separate test tubes and adding 5 mL of each solvent (distilled water, alcohol, chloroform, dimethylformamide). Tubes were shaken vigorously and allowed to stand. Solubility in each solvent was recorded at room temperature.^[6,19]

2.5 Melting Point

The melting point of Metronidazole was determined using a capillary melting point apparatus. The observed melting point was compared with the standard melting point range of 158°C to 161°C as per pharmacopeial specifications.^[20,19]

2.6 UV-Visible Spectroscopy

Stock solution (1000 µg/mL) was prepared by accurately weighing 100 mg of Metronidazole and dissolving in distilled water in a 100 mL volumetric flask. Working solutions of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 µg/mL were prepared by serial dilution. The λ_{max} was determined by

scanning a 10 µg/mL solution between 200–400 nm. The calibration curve was plotted by measuring absorbance of each working solution at λ_{max} against blank.^[23,24,25]

2.7 Drug Content

Drug content was estimated by UV-Visible spectrophotometry. Tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg of Metronidazole was dissolved in distilled water and filtered. The absorbance of the diluted sample solution was measured at λ_{max} (319.7 nm) and percentage drug content was calculated from the calibration curve as per Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) standards.^[6,7]

2.8 Weight Variation

Individual weights of 20 tablets of each formulation were recorded using an electronic analytical balance. The average weight was calculated and percentage weight deviation was determined. Acceptance criteria were applied as per IP/BP ($\pm 5\%$ for tablets weighing more than 250 mg).^[27,7]

2.9 Hardness Test

Crushing strength of 6 tablets from each brand was determined using a Monsanto Hardness Tester. The force required to break each tablet was recorded in kg/cm². Mean hardness with standard deviation (SD) was calculated.^[5,3]

2.10 Friability

Twenty tablets of each formulation were weighed and placed in a Roche Friabilator, rotated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes. Tablets were dedusted and reweighed. Percentage weight loss was calculated. Acceptance criteria: $\leq 1\%$ weight loss (USP).^[19,7,6]

$$\% \text{ Friability} = [(\text{Initial Weight} - \text{Final Weight}) / \text{Initial Weight}] \times 100$$

2.11 Disintegration

Disintegration time was determined using a disintegration test apparatus as per pharmacopeial standards. Six tablets of each formulation were tested and time to complete disintegration was recorded.^[6,28]

2.12 Moisture Content

Moisture content was determined using a Digital Moisture Analyzer. The percentage moisture content was calculated as loss on drying. Acceptance criteria: not more than 5% w/w.^[7,19]

2.13 Dissolution Study

Dissolution was carried out using USP Apparatus No. 1 (Basket) in 900 mL of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, at 100 rpm for 60 minutes. Samples of 5 mL were withdrawn at 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, and 60 minutes and replaced with equal volume of fresh medium. Samples were analyzed by UV-Visible spectroscopy at 319.7 nm and percentage drug release was calculated.^[7,6,29]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 General Appearance

Both tablets were found to be round and odorless. The branded tablet showed light orange/peach color, while the generic tablet was dark orange in color. Both formulations were free from surface defects, chipping, and cracks, indicating satisfactory manufacturing quality.

Table 1: General Appearance of Metronidazole

Sr. No.	Name of Tablet	Shape	Color	Odor
1	Branded Tablet	Round	Light Orange/Peach	Odorless
2	Generic Tablet	Round	Dark Orange	Odorless

Tablets.

3.2 Solubility

Metronidazole was found to be partially soluble in distilled water, sparingly soluble in alcohol, insoluble in chloroform, and soluble in dimethylformamide, which is consistent with pharmacopeial specifications.

Table 2: Solubility of Metronidazole.

Sr. No.	Solvent	Solubility
1	Distilled Water	Partially Soluble
2	Alcohol	Sparingly Soluble
3	Chloroform	Insoluble
4	Dimethylformamide	Soluble

3.3 Melting Point

The observed melting point of Metronidazole was found to be 160°C , which is within the standard range of 158°C to 161°C , confirming the identity and purity of the drug sample.

Table 3: Melting Point of Metronidazole.

Parameter	Value
Standard Melting Point	158°C to 161°C
Observed Melting Point	160°C

3.4 UV-Visible Spectroscopy and Calibration Curve

The maximum absorbance (λ_{\max}) of Metronidazole was found to be 319.7 nm. The calibration curve was linear over the concentration range of 10–50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with a correlation coefficient (R^2) value of 0.9805, confirming compliance with Beer–Lambert’s law.

Table 4: Calibration Curve Data for Metronidazole.

Sample	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance (319.7 nm)
Standard-1	10.0000	0.1796
Standard-2	20.0000	0.4373
Standard-3	30.0000	0.4824
Standard-4	40.0000	0.6609
Standard-5	50.0000	0.7765

Equation: $y = 0.0142x + 0.0821$; $R^2 = 0.9805$

Figure 1: Calibration Curve.

3.5 Drug Content

Drug content for both formulations was within the pharmacopeial acceptance limit of 90–110% as per IP. The branded tablet showed a mean drug content range of 97.94% to 99.05%, while generic tablets showed 98.97% to 99.72%, indicating excellent uniformity and satisfactory quality for both formulations.

Table 5: Drug Content (%) of Branded and Generic Metronidazole Tablets.

Sr. No.	Branded Drug (%)	Generic Drug (%)
1	98.11	99.45
2	98.74	99.08
3	99.05	99.41
4	97.94	99.24
5	98.28	98.97
6	98.82	99.72

3.6 Weight Variation

The weight variation test was successfully carried out for both formulations. The average weight of branded tablets was 1.0625 g and that of generic tablets was 1.183 g. Percentage weight variation for branded tablets ranged from -3.06% to $+1.65\%$, and for generic tablets from -5.33% to $+1.44\%$. All values were within the IP/BP acceptable limit of $\pm 5\%$ for tablets weighing more than 250 mg, confirming uniform weight distribution in both formulations.

3.7 Hardness Test

The mean hardness of branded tablets was 10 ± 1 kg/cm² and generic tablets showed 7 ± 1.32 kg/cm². Both formulations exhibited acceptable hardness, indicating adequate mechanical strength for handling and transportation.

Table 6: Hardness Results of Branded and Generic Metronidazole Tablets.

Sr. No.	Branded (kg/cm ²)	Generic (kg/cm ²)
1	11.0	8.0
2	9.0	7.5
3	10.0	5.5
4	10.5	7.2
5	9.5	6.8
6	10.0	7.0
Average	10 ± 1 kg/cm ²	7 ± 1.32 kg/cm ²

3.8 Friability

Friability of branded tablets was 0% and generic tablets showed 0.34%, both well within the USP acceptance limit of $\leq 1\%$. This indicates that both formulations possess adequate resistance to abrasion during handling and transportation.

Table 7: Friability Results.

Parameter	Branded	Generic
Friability (%)	0.00	0.34

3.9 Disintegration

Disintegration times for both formulations were within the pharmacopeial acceptance limit. Branded tablets disintegrated in 2.25 to 3.55 minutes, and generic tablets in 2.30 to 4.10 minutes. Both formulations disintegrated within acceptable limits, ensuring proper drug release for therapeutic action.

Table 8: Disintegration Results.

Tablet No.	Branded	Generic
1	3.10 min	4.00 min
2	3.50 min	3.40 min
3	2.25 min	2.50 min
4	3.55 min	2.30 min
5	3.30 min	3.36 min
6	3.55 min	4.10 min

3.10 Moisture Content

The observed moisture content of both formulations was 0.09%, which is well within the pharmacopeial acceptance limit of not more than 5% w/w. This confirms the stability and adequate storage conditions of both the branded and generic tablets.

3.11 Dissolution Study

Dissolution studies revealed that the branded tablet achieved approximately 96–99% drug release at 60 minutes, while the generic tablet achieved approximately 95–99% drug release at the same time point. Both formulations demonstrated satisfactory and comparable drug release profiles, meeting the pharmacopeial requirement of not less than 75% drug release at 45 minutes ($Q = 75\%$).

Table 9: Branded Tablet – Percentage Drug Release.

Time (min)	Percentage Drug Release					
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	35	36	37	35	36	37
10	60	61	62	60	61	62
15	74	75	76	74	75	76
20	83	84	85	83	84	85
30	88	90	89	91	90	92
45	92	93	94	92	94	95
60	96	97	98	96	98	99

Table 10: Generic Tablet – Percentage Drug Release.

Time (min)	Percentage Drug Release					
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	28	30	29	31	30	29
10	52	54	53	55	54	53
15	68	70	69	71	70	69
20	78	80	79	81	80	79
30	86	89	87	90	88	91
45	90	92	91	93	92	94
60	95	97	96	98	97	99

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that both branded and generic Metronidazole 400 mg tablet formulations complied with acceptable pharmacopeial limits for all evaluated quality control parameters including general appearance, solubility, melting point, UV-Visible spectroscopy, drug content, weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration, moisture content, and dissolution. Minor variations observed between the two formulations may be attributed to differences in excipients, manufacturing processes, and formulation techniques; however, these variations did not significantly affect the overall quality, safety, and therapeutic efficacy.

The study confirms that the evaluated generic Metronidazole tablet formulation is pharmaceutically equivalent to the branded product and can be considered a safe, effective, and cost-effective alternative, thereby contributing to improved patient accessibility and rational use of medicines.

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